

Factors Determining Glass Ceiling That Influences Women Career Development

A Study On Selected Private Commercial Banks in Dhaka City

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Abstract

The participation of women in different job fields in our country is inevitable for the economic development because half of the population of our country is women and most of them are young and educated. Moreover, in recent years, private banking sector has become successful to grab the attention of the graduates. Although a good number of women are working in different private banks, it has been seen that a few of them can reach their expected level of career. And there are lots of factors working behind this. This study has been conducted aiming at measuring the impact of various factors of glass ceiling which impede women career development. Anderson (1996) formula has been used to determine the sample size of the respondents from five purposively selected private commercial banks in Dhaka City. A structured questionnaire (Reliability test: Cronbach's Alpha .801) was sent to the respondents and the study found that long working hours, concern for children, coworkers' appreciation in workplace, negativity in competitiveness of women, years of experience, work-related competencies have impact on women career development. The study ended with some recommendations, which will help the decision makers for further progress.

Keywords: Glass Ceiling (GC), Women Career Development, Private Commercial Banks

Introduction

The economic condition of a country is measured by the living standard of the people of that country. In recent year, the Per Capita Income of the people of our country has increased to 1610 USD (BBS, 2016 - 2017). The participation of both male and female has helped us to achieve this success. Like other sectors, banking sector is also vital for the development of a country where a huge number of female employees are engaged with active participation

The participation of women in different levels of the organization is not up to the expectation. As per the editorial, the New Age (2015), percentage of female staff in the banking sector decreased significantly in 2014 compared with that of 2013 as most of the banks are reluctant to recruit them, said officials of Bangladesh Bank. According to latest Bangladesh Bank data, the entry-level female staff decreased to 13.70% of the total newly-recruited staff in 2014 from 16.88% in 2013. The mid-level female staff in the banking sector decreased to 14.18% in 2014 from 16.66% in 2013 while the female participation in the senior management of the banks declined to 7.46% from 10.91%. The number of female staff, aged between 30 years and 50 years, decreased to 12.98% in 2014 from 15.64% in 2013 while the woman staff aged over 50 years declined to 6.91% from

9.61%. The female participation in the board of directors of the banks also decreased in the period as the ratio stood at 11.27% against 13.73% in 2013. That's why here comes to our mind the concept of 'Glass Ceiling'.

In general, glass ceiling (GC) refers to the invisible barriers that restraint female employees from getting promoted into the upper positions in an organization though they are capable enough to handle the position. Cotter et al. (2001) have identified four criteria creating GC scenario inside an organization. According to their statement, a GC inequality stands for gender or racial

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differences not described by other job-relevant characteristics of the employees. They also mentioned that the gender or racial difference is greater at higher levels of an outcome than at lower levels of an outcome. Here, GC inequality symbolizes the disparity that tends to increase over courses of career. Generally, women are assumed to have larger responsibilities than men do. Consequently, women are avoided by their employers to promote for the higher positions because women as a group are assumed to be absent from work more often than men due to childbearing and childcare responsibilities (Rosenfeld et al., 1998).

A survey conducted by UNDP in 1993 identified six perceptions of unequal treatment to women in the administrative cadre of the BCS (Bangladesh

Civil Service). These perceptions were: (a) negative attitudes toward women by male colleagues, (b) hesitation of superiors about the capabilities of women officers, (c) superiority complexes of male colleagues, (d) intention of men to treat women in a gender-biased fashion, (e) belief in traditional thought that men are more efficient than women, and (f) non-cooperation of male colleagues. These perceptions induce working women to prefer their families to career advancement.

Career development is the lifelong process of managing, learning, work, leisure, and transitions in order to move toward a personally determined and evolving preferred future. As Mathis and Jackson (2000) state career development helps organizations to magnetize and hold effective and efficient employees. Similarly, this facilitates the employees to attain their individual career goals and objectives. A combined effort of the organizations, employees, their families and wider society is crucial for successful career development. Due to the absence of any of these efforts, both men and women

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may confront many challenges as they advance through careers. Reasons for difficulties in career opportunities for women have been identified by various researchers over time, since the existence of GC in the organizations has obtained considerable attention in recent years.

Statement of the Problem

Although various studies have been conducted on GC in different sectors, but a very little attention has been paid by researchers on banking industry, especially on women employees working in different private commercial banks in Dhaka city. The purpose of the study is to realize whether the women employees working in private commercial banks in

Dhaka city confronting obstacles in case of advancing their career due to GC. For the attainment of the purpose following things are required to be analyzed:

1. Whether individual factors (such as - years of experience, academic excellence, work related competencies) representing GC are influencing the career development of women employees working in private commercial banks in Dhaka city.
2. Whether family factors (such as - life partner's support, concern about children, family size) are influencing the career development of women employees.

3. Whether organizational factors (such as -opportunities for career advancement, attitude of management towards having female superiors and having competencies in women, management's reluctance in assigning females in challenging tasks) are influencing the career development of women employees. and
4. Whether cultural factors (such as-ethnicity and religious issues) representing GC are influencing the career development of women employees.

Objectives of the Study

It is commonly believed that women employees get less chance for career advancement than men employees. The study is conducted to find out the following objectives:

1. To find out the factors determining GC influencing the career development of women working in private commercial banks of Dhaka city;
2. To measure the impact of GC on career development of female employees of private commercial banks of Dhaka city; and
3. To recommend solutions for overcoming the barriers standing in the way of women career development.

Limitations of the Study

In spite of sincere efforts, the study has gone through the following limitations:

1. The sample of employees do not represent the total work force;
2. The study is based on employees' perception which may change over time; and
3. There was limitation of time and money to conduct the study.

Review of Literature

As Afza and Newaz (2008) state, Carol Hymowitz and Timothy Schellhardt identified the term 'Glass Ceiling (GC)' for the first time in an article that was published on the March 24th edition of the Wall Street Journal in 1986. The article reveals the imperceptible barriers impeding the career advancement of women in the

American workforce. Before the identification by Carol Hymowitz and Timothy Schellhardt, the term 'Glass Ceiling' was coined by two women at Hewlett Packard in 1979, Katherine Lawrence and Marianne Schreiber. They used this term to illustrate a situation that described though there seemed to be a clear path of promotion, but practically women seemed unable to progress beyond.

The metaphor 'Glass Ceiling' has been described as the barriers restraining women from ascending to senior management positions in large organizations, but here the barriers are assumed to be transparent in nature as they are not easily identifiable. Basically, these barriers are confronted and realized by women employees as they try to move up the corporate ladder (Morrison et. al., 1987). They thought that the ongoing prejudice and discrimination against women employees in

the workplace are responsible for the scarcity of female leaders. This situation explains that in spite of being capable of moving to upper levels at some points the female employees are halted by invisible barriers and this happens to them as a group, who are kept from advancing higher, because they are women.

The term 'glass ceiling' also implies that gender disparities are more prevalent at the top of hierarchies than at lower levels, and that the disadvantages become more challenging as a person's career advances (Cotter et al., 1999). However, a study conducted by US Department of Labor in 1991 stated that substantial GC barriers were encountered by women and minorities in their careers. They experienced these barriers in their professions more than previously thought. Researchers have found a lot of factors contributing to the GC barriers. According to Bombuwela and Chamaru (2013), factors contributing to GC barriers include sexual, ethnic, racial, religious discrimination or harassment in the workplace, existing culture of the business organizations, lack of family-friendly workplace policies etc.

Cotter et al. (2001) concluded like that, though evidence of GC was found by them, racial inequalities among men did not follow the similar pattern. Kanter (1997) mentioned that men in managerial positions generally prefer and tend to

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appoint people with cultural preferences similar to their own or people similar in the respect to others already employed in the organization. This kind of homo sociality basically makes men prefer other men for self-reflection, relaxation and social support. Men may act like that to confirm their own identity and cultural norms (Lipman-Blumen, 1976; Maume, 1999). Another reason behind difficulties in career opportunities for women may be the attitude of management toward having female leaders in top positions of the organization. In that case, management perceives that men are better suited to leadership positions than are women (Kanter, 1997; Reskin and Hartmann, (eds) 1986).

Men in strategies could use such attitude to secure power, authority and other privileges (Acker, 1990). Research on GC in Bangladesh is very limited and unexplored. Previous research works done by

Zafarullah (2000) and UNDP (1999) on GC is to identify the factors creating GC effects in different organizations and service sectors in Bangladesh. A study conducted by Afza and Newaz (2008) focused on factors determining the presence of GC and influencing women career advancement in Bangladesh. From the study they have found that, management's perception and work environment are most significant factors in case of creating glass ceiling in an organization. In addition to organizational policy and work life conflict have been identified as second most significant factor contributing to the GC effect in the organization.

Career development refers to a lifelong process of becoming conscious of, exploring and experiencing factors that influence a variety of aspects of a person's life. Knowledge, skills and attitudes evolved through this path of discovery enable planning and decision making

not only about employment and vocational choices but also about personal management and work skills (Greenhaus et al., 2010). Women have reported that, in comparison with men, greater barriers have been confronted by themselves in getting career development opportunities (Armstrong, 2003). These barriers, termed as GC, may be faced by the women due to individual, family, social and organizational factors while developing through their careers (Afza and Newaz, 2008). The impact of GC may differ in different countries and in different sectors. This research is aimed to analyze the impacts of GC on women career development in private banking sector of Bangladesh.

Methodology of The Study

Sampling and Sample Size

The present study was conducted on a sample of ninety (90) employees from five, purposively selected, private commercial banks in Dhaka City having total 1225 female employees (72 of NRB Commercial Bank Ltd., 176 of Dutch-Bangla Bank Ltd., 342 of Southeast Bank Ltd., 285 of United Commercial Bank Ltd., 350 of Bank Asia Ltd.). The sample percentage is normally distributed. For calculating sample size following formula has been used:

$$\text{Sample Size, } n = \frac{N P Q}{\frac{(N-1)e}{z} + P Q}$$

Where,

N = population size;

z = the selected critical value of desired confidence level;

P = the estimated proportion of an attribute that is present in the population;

Q = 1- p; and

e = the desired level of precision (margin of error).

(Weirs, 2005; Newbold, et.al., 2003; Davis, et.al., 2002; Anderson, et.al., 1996; Mendenhall & Reinmuth, 1982)

Assuming the maximum variability, which is equal to 50% (P = 0.5), (Q = 1-P), with ±10% precision (margin of error) and taking 95% confidence level the standard score (z = 1.96) arises.

$$n = \frac{1225 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{\frac{(1225 - 1) \cdot 10^2}{1.96^2} + 0.5 \times 0.5}$$

n = 89.1253 or 90

Questionnaire Development and Data Collection

A specially designed, 14-item questionnaire was constructed based on literature review, taking opinion from experts and from prospective respondents. Before finalizing the questionnaire, a pilot survey was also conducted, and necessary adjustments were made in the questionnaire. A total 130 questionnaires were delivered through personal visit,

and email. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) to measure respondents' responses. Secondary data were collected from various articles, national and international journals, doctoral theses, periodicals, and different online sources.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data were analyzed using SPSS 20.0. 'Strongly disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neutral', 'Agree', and 'Strongly agree' were coded as 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 respectively.

Frequency distribution, mean, and standard deviation are used to analyze the data.

Results and Discussions

Nowadays participation of women employees in different work field has increased. Banking sector is one of them where females are highly encouraged to work in. As we are trying to evaluate the impact of GC on women career development, we collected responses from 90 respondents to fulfill our objectives. Their demographic information is shown as under:

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No of Items
.800	.801	14

Table 2: Demographic Information of the Respondents (N=90)

	Frequency (f)	
Respondents' Age Level	25-35	28 31.11%
	Between 35-45	41 45.56%
	More than 45	21 23.33%
Respondents' Educational level	Graduation	10 11.11%
	Post-Graduation	71 78.89%
	Other Degrees	09 10.00%
Respondents' Designations	Lower level officer	31 34.45%
	Mid-level officer	47 52.22%
	Top level officer	12 13.33%
Respondents' Years of experiences	Less than 7years	33 36.67%
	8-15 years	47 52.22%
	More than 15 years	10 11.11%
Respondents' Monthly Income Status (BDT 000's)	25-50	24 26.67%
	50-75	32 35.56%
	75-100	20 22.23%
	More than 100	14 15.56%
Respondents' Marital Status	Married	72 80.00%
	Unmarried	18 20.00%
Respondents' Children Status	Yes	43 59.73%
	No	29 40.27%

Source: Field Survey and from Human Resource Department of respective banks

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As the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient (Table 1) for the 14 items is 0.801, which is greater than .70, it means that the items have relatively higher internal consistency.

From the Table 2 it is clear that most of the respondents are between the age of 35 to 45 and holds post-graduation degree. Again, the majority of the respondents worked at mid-level having experience of 8 to 15 years with monthly income ranging from 50 to 75 thousand Taka. Our study shows that 80% employees are married where 59.73% have children.

The mean and standard deviation of the demographic information of the respondents are shown in Table 3. Here the mean age of the respondents is 39.22 years which means most of the respondents are working at mid-level having experience of more than 9 years (9.34 years) and their average income is 69.17 thousand BDT.

The Table 4 shows the mean and standard deviation and number of respondents. From the results we can conclude that factors like work related competencies, long working hours in job, concern about children, participation in decision-making is appreciated by superiors and coworkers, male employees tend to grip on the powerful positions of the organization are important variables liable for affecting women career development.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	90	39.22	.835
Education	90	2.17	.375
Experience	90	1.90	.835
Income	90	69.17	1.126
Marital status	90	.80	.402
No. of Children	90	.48	.502
Valid N (list wise)	90		

Table 4: Independent Variables			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
Years of experience are fairly considered	2.26	.955	90
Academic excellence, specialized training and courses contribute in case of promotion	2.26	.955	90
Work related competencies play a vital role in terms of career development	3.70	1.106	90
Long working hours in job is appreciated by family members	3.61	.817	90
Life-partner provides both family and job-related support	2.80	.997	90
Concern about children hampers job performance	3.49	.503	90
Sufficient opportunities exist for women to advance into senior management position	2.56	.973	90
Having female superior create discomfort for male employees	2.22	1.139	90
Management shows reluctance in assigning female employees for challenging projects	2.22	.921	90
Male employees tend to grip on the powerful positions of the organization	2.89	1.203	90
Competitiveness in women is considered negatively at work	2.67	.948	90
Participation in decision-making is appreciated by superiors and coworkers	3.33	.948	90
Women confront deprivation in case of getting financial benefits	1.86	.572	90
Ethnicity and religious issues are considered in promoting into higher position	1.63	.626	90

The output from communalities show the variance in the variables accounted by the extracted factors (Table 5). Fair consideration of years of experience (98.2%); academic excellence, specialized training and courses contribute in case of promotion (98.2%); negativity in competitiveness of women at work (86.6%), and participation in decision-making by superiors and coworkers (86.6%) show high variability while consideration of ethnicity and religious issues, and long working hours in job is appreciated by family members show less variability.

Major Findings

The study found that women career development is highly influenced by factors like concern about children, coworkers' appreciation in workplace, long working hours in job, mentality of male employees to grip the higher and powerful positions, negativity in competitiveness of women at work. The result also shows that respondents believe that factors like work related competencies, years of experience, academic excellence, specialized training and courses could help them in career development. Activists, working for women, also criticize that the banks are reluctant to recruit female staff due to the provision of six-month maternity leave which is not profitable to banks. As per the observation of the high officials of the regulatory body for banks, it is also clear

Table 5: Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Years of experience are fairly considered in time of promotion	1.000	.982
Academic excellence, specialized training and courses contribute in case of promotion	1.000	.982
Work related competencies play a vital role in terms of career development	1.000	.805
Long working hours in job is appreciated by family members	1.000	.576
Life-partner provides both family and job-related support	1.000	.601
Concern about children hampers job performance	1.000	.805
Sufficient opportunities exist for women to advance into senior management position	1.000	.760
Having female superior create discomfort for male employees	1.000	.864
Management shows reluctance in assigning female employees for challenging projects	1.000	.847
Male employees tend to grip on the powerful positions of the organization	1.000	.854
Competitiveness in women is considered negatively at work	1.000	.866
Participation in decision-making is appreciated by superiors and coworkers	1.000	.866
Women confront deprivation in case of getting financial benefits	1.000	.677
Ethnicity and religious issues are considered in promoting into higher position	1.000	.484
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis		

that the dropped out female staff was also substantial as the banks were usually reluctant to promote women due to male-dominated attitude. Along with this male-dominated attitude, competitiveness of women at work is seen negatively which is like the study conducted by UNDP in 1993. Again, the study and observation of experienced bankers and scholars found that many female employees generally left the job due to social and family related bindings like taking care of their

children or shifting to new places due to their husbands' profession, and consequently often fail to reach senior management level.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has endeavored to examine the impact of GC on women career development in private commercial banking sector of Dhaka City. The study found some factors that have both positive and negative impact on career development

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of women. Factors like work related competencies, years of experience, and academic excellence etc. need to be focused while factors like negativity in competitiveness of women at work, mentality of male employees to grip the higher and powerful positions need to be minimized. The following recommendations might be beneficial for both the organizations and women employees.

Since women having children at home need to pay extra concern that may hamper their performance at work, organization can arrange day care program. In addition, organization should encourage women participation in decision making to prove their capabilities. If women can prove their capabilities once, it will help male employees get out of the mentality to grip the powerful positions and grow positive mentality regarding the competitiveness of women. We believe that this study will help the stakeholders especially the policy makers.

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